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TM4C123GH6PZ MCU Based Intelligent Car

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Intelligent Car Design

Abstract:

This report presents the design and implementation of a car capable of line following and self-balancing using the TM4C123GH6PZ MCU. The car incorporates a 12-Gray Sensor for line detection, an Ultra-Sonic Sound Sensor for obstacle detection, two motors, and a motor driver. The MCU serves as the central controller, processing sensor data and executing algorithms for line following and self-balancing. The line following algorithm uses real-time data from the 12-Gray Sensor to keep the car aligned with the line. The self-balancing algorithm maintains stability by monitoring the tilt angle and making corrective adjustments. Challenges such as sensor calibration and motor control were addressed through testing and adjustments. Evaluation demonstrated accurate line following, stable self-balancing, and efficient obstacle avoidance. The integration of components enabled autonomous navigation and safe operation. The car design achieved line following and self-balancing using the TM4C123GH6PZ MCU. Future improvements could include sensor fusion and advanced obstacle avoidance. This project showcases the potential of embedded systems in creating intelligent autonomous vehicles.

Keywords: TM4C123GH6PZ, Motor Driver, Gray Sensor, Line Following etc.

Table of Contents

1. Introduction.....	5
1.1 System Modules.....	5
1.2 System Composition.....	7
1.3 Summary.....	10
2. Installation and Construction of IDE.....	11
2.1 Introduction of Keil.....	11
2.2 Construction and Configuration.....	12
2.3 Complete Download, Installation and Compilation Process.....	13
2.3.1 Download Keil uVision.....	13
2.3.2 Installation process of Keil uVision 5.....	16
2.3.3 Compilation and Program Download Process.....	22
3. Core Algorithms.....	26
3.1 Introduction of Algorithms.....	26
3.2 Principles of Algorithms.....	27
3.3 Visual View of Algorithm.....	28
3.3.1 Line Following Algorithm.....	28
3.3.2 Self-Balancing Algorithm.....	29
3.4 PID Controlling.....	30
4. Measurement and Analysis.....	32
4.1 Program design.....	32
4.2 Results Analysis.....	34
4.2.1 Line Following Result Analysis.....	35
4.2.2 Self Balancing Result Analysis.....	36
5. Summary.....	37
Attachment A: System Hardware Picture.....	38
Attachment B: Code.....	40
Attachment C: Photo Taken Together.....	47

1. Introduction

The design and implementation of a car capable of line following and self-balancing using the TM4C123GH6PZ MCU has been introduced in this report. The objective of the project was to create an autonomous vehicle that can navigate along a designated line and maintain balance without external intervention. The car incorporates a 12-Gray Sensor for line detection, an Ultra-Sonic Sound Sensor for obstacle detection, two motors, and a motor driver. The TM4C123GH6PZ MCU serves as the central controller, processing sensor data and executing algorithms for line following and self-balancing. This introduction provides an overview of the project and highlights the significance of line following and self-balancing in autonomous vehicles.

1.1 System Modules

The designed car for line following and self-balancing consists of the following components:

- i. **TM4C123GH6PZ Microcontroller:** The TM4C123GH6PZ microcontroller unit serves as the central processing unit of the car. It receives input from various sensors, processes data, and controls the motors and motor driver based on the implemented algorithms.

Fig 1.1. TM4C123GH6PZ Microcontroller

- ii. **12-Gray Sensor:** The 12-Gray Sensor is a key component for line following. It consists of multiple infrared sensors that detect the contrast between the line and the surface beneath the car. These sensors provide information about the position of the line, enabling the MCU to make necessary adjustments for precise line following.

Fig 1.2. Gray Sensor

- iii. **Motors:** The car is equipped with two motors that provide the necessary torque for propulsion and maneuverability. These motors drive the wheels and enable the car to move forward, backward, and turn in response to the control signals from the MCU.
- iv. **Motor Driver:** The motor driver acts as an interface between the MCU and the motors. It amplifies the control signals received from the MCU and provides the appropriate power and direction to the motors. The motor driver ensures precise control over the motor's speed and direction, enabling accurate movement and navigation.

Fig 1.3. Motor Driver

- v. **Car Body:** The components need to be arranged in a proper way. That's why the car requires a car body to hold the components.

Fig 1.4. Car Body

The integration of these components forms a cohesive system that enables the car to perform line following and self-balancing tasks. The MCU processes the sensor data from the 12-Gray Sensor and Ultra-Sonic Sound Sensor to implement the line following algorithm and obstacle avoidance strategies. The control signals generated by the MCU are transmitted to the motor driver, which in turn controls the motors to achieve the desired movement and balance of the car.

1.2 System Composition

To connect the components in your car design, you need to establish proper electrical connections between them. Here's a general guideline on how to connect the components:

Connect the TM4C123GH6PZ MCU:

- Identify the necessary pins on the MCU for communication and control.
- Connect the power supply (VCC and GND) to the appropriate pins on the MCU.
- Establish communication interfaces, such as UART, SPI, or I2C, based on the requirements of the other components.
- Connect the control pins of the motor driver to the MCU, ensuring proper mapping for motor control.

Fig 1.5. PIN Diagram of TM4C123GH6PZ

Connect the 12-Gray Sensor:

- Identify the output pins of the 12-Gray Sensor.
- Connect the output pins of the sensor to the input pins of the MCU.
- Consider the communication interface required by the sensor (e.g., analog or digital).

Fig 1.6. Connect Gray Sensor with MCU

Connect the Motors:

- Identify the connection terminals on the motors.
- Connect the motor terminals to the output pins of the motor driver.
- Ensure proper polarity and wiring configuration for the motors.

Fig 1.7. Motos Connected with Motor Controller and Wheels

Connect the Motor Driver:

- Identify the control pins of the motor driver.
- Connect the control pins to the output pins of the MCU.
- Ensure proper mapping and configuration of the control signals.

Fig 1.8. Motor Controller Connection Example

Provide Power Supply:

- Determine the power requirements of each component.
- Connect the power supply source to the appropriate pins of each component, ensuring proper voltage and current levels.

Fig 1.9. 1200 mAh Power Supply

Remember to refer to the datasheets and technical documentation of each component for specific pin configurations, voltage levels, and communication protocols.

It's important to plan and document your connections carefully to avoid any potential wiring errors or shorts. Consider using a breadboard, soldering, or specific connectors to establish secure and reliable connections. Additionally, label or document your connections to make troubleshooting and future modifications easier.

1.3 Summary

The TM4C123GH6PZ MCU acts as the brain of the car, processing sensor data and executing algorithms for line following and self-balancing. It receives inputs from the 12-Gray Sensor to accurately track and follow lines, and from the Ultra-Sonic Sound Sensor to detect obstacles and avoid collisions. The MCU generates control signals based on the sensor inputs and sends them to the motor driver.

The 12-Gray Sensor provides information about the position of the line relative to the car, enabling precise line following. The Ultra-Sonic Sound Sensor measures obstacle distances, allowing the car to navigate in dynamic environments by adjusting its path or coming to a stop when necessary.

The motors are responsible for providing the necessary torque for propulsion and maneuverability. The motor driver amplifies the control signals from the MCU and controls the motors, enabling the car to move in different directions and make turns as directed by the algorithms.

2. Installation and Construction of IDE

Keil uVision 5 is an integrated development environment (IDE) developed by Arm, specifically designed for programming and debugging microcontrollers. It provides a comprehensive set of tools for embedded software development, including code editing, compilation, debugging, and simulation.

2.1 Introduction of Keil

The primary goal of Keil uVision is to streamline the development process and provide a complete solution for embedded systems programming. It offers a powerful code editor with advanced features like syntax highlighting, auto-completion, and code navigation, enhancing productivity and code quality. The IDE incorporates a build system and the Arm C/C++ Compiler, enabling efficient code compilation for various microcontroller architectures.

One of the key strengths of Keil uVision lies in its comprehensive debugging capabilities. The integrated debugger allows developers to perform real-time debugging, stepping through code, setting breakpoints, and monitoring variables. This enables efficient code troubleshooting, optimization, and verification, ensuring the software functions as intended on the target microcontroller.

Keil uVision also supports simulation and emulation, allowing developers to test their code in a virtual environment before deploying it on actual hardware. This feature-rich simulation environment provides a cost-effective and safe way to validate software functionality, simulate peripherals, and evaluate system behavior.

Furthermore, Keil uVision offers extensive device support, with a wide range of

microcontroller devices from different manufacturers integrated into the IDE. This simplifies the process of configuring and programming microcontrollers, providing a seamless development experience.

2.2 Construction and Configuration

To configure Keil uVision for the TM4C123GH6PZ microcontroller, we have followed these steps:

1. Start by opening Keil uVision on your computer.
2. Create a new project by selecting "Project" from the menu and then choosing "New μ Vision Project."
3. Specify the project name and location. Click "Save" to create the project.
4. In the "Select Device for Target" window, search for "TM4C123GH6PZ" in the search bar or navigate to "Texas Instruments" -> "Tiva C Series" -> "TM4C123GH6PZ" and select it. Click "OK" to continue.
5. Now, you need to select the startup file for your project. Right-click on your project name in the "Project" window, select "Options," and navigate to the "Target" tab.
6. Under the "Code Generation" section, select the appropriate startup file. Typically, it will be "startup_TM4C123.s" for the TM4C123GH6PZ microcontroller.
7. Next, configure the necessary settings for your project. This includes selecting the toolchain, specifying compiler options, linker settings, and any other project-specific configurations.
8. Set up the debug settings by going to the "Options" menu, selecting the "Debug" tab, and choosing the appropriate debugger for your setup.
9. Connect your TM4C123GH6PZ microcontroller to your computer using a suitable debug adapter, such as an ARM-JTAG or ARM-SWD probe.
10. Build your project by clicking on the "Build" icon or selecting "Build" from the "Project" menu. This will compile your code and generate the necessary binary file.

11. If you want to debug your code, click on the "Start/Stop Debug Session" icon or choose "Start/Stop Debug Session" from the "Debug" menu. This will launch the debugger and allow you to step through your code, set breakpoints, and monitor variables.

2.3 Complete Download, Installation and Compilation Process

2.3.1 Download Keil uVision

- Keil download source: <https://www.keil.com>
- This will open the web browser page as shown in the figure below:

- From the list given on the top of this web page select download as shown in the figure below:

- When you click on this section the webpage giving the downloads option will appear as shown in the figure below:

- As is obvious from the description given under the name of each of the category the product downloads will give you the setup of the keil ide and the file downloads will provide you some of the sample codes that are built and run on keil.
- We here need to download the IDE first and install it afterwards so that we can implement our coding portion using this IDE so the category we should select here is product downloads as shown in the figure below:

- When you click on this category the following webpage will appear as shown in the figure below:

- As here we are interested in downloading an IDE for TIVA TM4C123G which a Cortex and ARM device hence we must download a developing environment for Cortex and ARM devices i.e. MDK-ARM.
- This will show you a window asking you to fill out the form for your personal information only for the company record. The form that will be displayed is shown in the figure below:

- Fill out the form shown in the above figure and press submit this will show you a page showing the features and the setup file for MDK-arm as shown in the figure

below:

- The mdk526.exe file shown in the figure above shows the setup file for the Keil u vision version 5.26 which is the latest version of Keil so far.
- Click on the .EXE file at the bottom of the page as shown in the figure below, this file contains the setup of Keil.

PDF files may be opened with Acrobat Reader.
ZIP files may be opened with PKZIP or WINZIP.

- After you click on the file your PC will ask you were to save the setup (.exe) file. Select the folder of designation where you want to save the file and hit enter as shown in the figure below:

2.3.2 Installation process of Keil uVision 5

- The size of the setup file is around 900Mb it will take some time to download in your PC from the online source. Wait for the download to complete before proceeding further.
- After the download is complete the downloaded folder will be placed in the folder you designated it during the installation time as shown in the figure below:

Name	Date modified	Type	Size
Keil uVision 5	11-Sep-18 8:19 AM	File folder	
data sheet whole	17-Sep-16 2:14 PM	PDF File	21,355 KB
en.stsw-link009	09-Dec-16 10:40 AM	WinRAR ZIP archive	5,187 KB
st-link_v2_usbdriver	10-May-11 7:14 AM	Application	11,299 KB
stm32f429-master	08-Apr-16 11:42 AM	WinRAR ZIP archive	161,373 KB

- The downloaded folder will already contain all the drivers needed to run the code and it also includes a pdf file that is the datasheet of the microcontroller TM4C123G as shown in the figure below:

- This data sheet also contains every little information about the microcontroller, its onboard pins, and also its libraries and alternate functionalities including all the

addresses of each pin.

- Now open the folder present inside the downloaded folder it will contain the setup file which needs to be installed.
- The name of both the folders will be the same because the external folder was only the drivers and datasheet inclusion folder and the main mdk file is inside the second nested folder. Inside the nested folder, the files shown in the figure below are present.

Name	Date modified	Type	Size
Driver Installation Demo	11-Sep-18 8:19 AM	File folder	
keil_c51v953.full.crack3d.by.morpheus	11-Sep-18 8:19 AM	File folder	
stellaris_icdi_drivers	11-Sep-18 8:19 AM	File folder	
keil_c51v953.full.crack3d.by.morpheus	12-Apr-16 10:29 AM	WinRAR archive	41 KB
MDK516a	05-Sep-15 3:07 AM	Application	463,353 KB

- This folder present here includes the necessary drivers and libraries needed to run simple code in Keil IDE. These folders are necessary for the successful installation of Keil and the version you downloaded will automatically install all the necessary drivers you just have to keep them in the same folder. From the folder select the setup file as shown in the figure below:

Name	Date modified	Type	Size
Driver Installation Demo	11-Sep-18 8:19 AM	File folder	
keil_c51v953.full.crack3d.by.morpheus	11-Sep-18 8:19 AM	File folder	
stellaris_icdi_drivers	11-Sep-18 8:19 AM	File folder	
keil_c51v953.full.crack3d.by.morpheus	12-Apr-16 10:29 AM	WinRAR archive	41 KB
MDK516a	05-Sep-15 3:07 AM	Application	463,353 KB

- Double click on this file and the setup will start installing necessary files for the IDE automatically. The setup will first ask for the administrative permission to made the required changes in your PC.
- Click yes and then the setup will show the window shown in the figure below:

- This is the welcome screen and it only shows the features of the Keil version to be installed and the products that will be downloaded automatically along with the setup.
- Simply click next and you don't have to do anything else here. The next screen after clicking the next button that will appear on the setup window is shown in the figure below:

- This page is the license agreement page. On this page, you agree to the terms and conditions required by the company to agree to in order to use any version of any of the products launched by that company.
- Check the highlighted arrow box as shown in the image above and click next to proceed with the installation part. The next window to be appeared is shown in the figure below:

- This window will ask you to select the folder where you want to install the Keil files, drivers, and libraries. Browse the designated folder where you want to place the libraries by clicking on the browse key and then click Next. The window that will appear after clicking the next key is shown in the figure below:

- In this window the setup will ask you to enter some necessary details i.e. personal information of the customer who is going to use the specified product to be installed here in the future.
- It has nothing to do with the installation and is only for the companies' record to keep a track of how many people are using there launched product and what are the companies or institutions they for which they are currently using the companies' product.

- Simply enter the first and last name of the (PC holder, most recommended), or the customer who is going to use the IDE. Enter the name of the company or institution you are currently working in and at the end enter your email ID and then click Next. The next window that will appear after clicking next is shown in the figure below:

- This is where the installation status of your product will be shown. It will take several minutes to install the setup. So, minimize the app and let the setup install all the drivers needed as it will do it automatically.
- The setup will automatically download all the required files you need not to do anything but to wait for the installation to complete. After all the drivers have been collected the setup will ask you for the permission of installation as shown in the figure below:

- This is where you give your consent that you want to install the IDE of Keil and the installation will begin.
- After the installation is complete the setup window will ask you to finish the installation successfully as shown in the figure below:

- After you finish the installation with the release note check box checked the setup will open the browser and show you the latest release of the notes of the Microcontroller Development kit (mdk) as shown in the figure below:

- But if you uncheck the box before finishing the installation this page will not be displayed and you can check these updates anytime in future using the link given below,
- Release notes: file:///C:/Keil_v5/ARM/HLP/Release_Notes.htm
- After that, a pac installer will open automatically and ask you for any updates you need now to install regarding the IDE. The pac installer is shown in the figure below:

That was the complete procedure to install Keil uVision 5.

2.3.3 Compilation and Program Download Process

- Open the Project file on Keil uVision 5 IDE

- We need to compile and build the project to generate downloadable file

- Build result

```
Build Output
compiling nclink.c...
compiling developer_mode.c...
compiling subtask.c...
linking...
Program Size: Code=97052 RO-data=9480 RW-data=3692 ZI-data=9908
FromELF: creating hex file...
".\Objects\TracklessSmartcar.axf" - 0 Error(s), 0 Warning(s).
Build Time Elapsed: 00:00:08
```

- Connect the car's MCU with ST-Link Debugger

- Configure the IDE to make it ready to download the program to the MCU

- Set ST-Link Debugger as target. Because in this project we have used the ST-Link Debugger to download the program to our Microcontroller

- Set the other parameters as shown below

- Start the Downloading process

```
Build Output
compiling developer_mode.c...
compiling subtask.c...
linking...
Program Size: Code=97052 RO-data=9480 RW-data=3692 ZI-data=9908
FromELF: creating hex file...
".\Objects\TracklessSmartcar.axf" - 0 Error(s), 0 Warning(s).
Build Time Elapsed: 00:00:08
Load "C:\\Users\\Md Shakib Hasan\\Desktop\\NController_V1.2.2 (Working)\\Objects\\TracklessSmartcar.axf"
Erase: 00016000H ST-Link Debugger t1: 0.00000000 sec L1: C1 CAP_NUM SCRL OVR: R,W
```

```
Build Output
Load "C:\\Users\\Md Shakib Hasan\\Desktop\\NController_V1.2.2 (Working)\\Objects\\TracklessSmartcar.axf"
Erase Done.
Programming Done.
Verify OK.
Application running ...
Flash Load finished at 02:05:11
Load "C:\\Users\\Md Shakib Hasan\\Desktop\\NController_V1.2.2 (Working)\\Objects\\TracklessSmartcar.axf"
Erase Done.
Program: 00003400H ST-Link Debugger t1: 0.00000000 sec L1: C1 CAP_NUM SCRL OVR: R,W
```

```
Build Output
Erase Done.
Programming Done.
Verify OK.
Application running ...
Flash Load finished at 02:06:11
Load "C:\\Users\\Md Shakib Hasan\\Desktop\\NController_V1.2.2 (Working)\\Objects\\TracklessSmartcar.axf"
Erase Done.
Programming Done.
Verify: 61 % ST-Link Debugger t1: 0.00000000 sec L1: C1 CAP_NUM SCRL OVR: R,W
```

- Download finished successfully.

```
Build Output
Application running ...
Flash Load finished at 02:06:11
Load "C:\\Users\\Md Shakib Hasan\\Desktop\\NController_V1.2.2 (Working)\\Objects\\TracklessSmartcar.axf"
Erase Done.
Programming Done.
Verify OK.
Application running ...
Flash Load finished at 02:06:22
<
ST-Link Debugger L1 C1 CAP NUM SCRL OVR R/W
```

3. Core Algorithms

3.1 Introduction of Algorithms

An algorithm is a set of instructions or rules that provide a step-by-step procedure for solving a specific problem or achieving a particular task. It is a well-defined and unambiguous sequence of operations aimed at efficiently solving a problem.

An algorithm takes inputs and produces outputs based on the given inputs and the steps performed during its execution. It is designed to be finite, meaning it will terminate after a finite number of steps. The steps of an algorithm are deterministic, ensuring that the same input will always yield the same output.

Efficiency is a crucial aspect of algorithm design. An algorithm should aim to solve the problem using minimal resources and in the least amount of time. Developing efficient algorithms can lead to improved performance, reduced complexity, and effective problem-solving.

Algorithms can be expressed using natural language, pseudocode, flowcharts, or programming languages. They are widely used in various domains, including mathematics, computer science, and data analysis. In computer science, algorithms form the foundation of computer programming and are essential for manipulating data, performing calculations, sorting and searching information, and more.

The design and analysis of algorithms are critical in optimizing processes, improving performance, and finding innovative solutions to complex problems. By developing well-structured and efficient algorithms, researchers and developers can tackle computational challenges effectively and create robust software solutions.

3.2 Principles of Algorithms

1. Initialize the car's components, including the TM4C123GH6PZ MCU, sensors, motors, and motor driver.
2. Set up the necessary variables and constants for controlling the car's behavior, such as speed, turning sensitivity, and balancing parameters.
3. Enter the main control loop:
 - 3.1. Read the sensor inputs from the 12-Gray Sensor and Ultra-Sonic Sound Sensor to gather information about the line and obstacles.
 - 3.2. Process the sensor data:
 - Use the 12-Gray Sensor to determine the position of the line relative to the car. Adjust the car's steering based on the line position, ensuring it stays centered on the line.
 - Utilize the Ultra-Sonic Sound Sensor to detect obstacles. If an obstacle is detected, take appropriate action, such as stopping or changing the car's direction to avoid the obstacle.
 - 3.3. Implement the self-balancing algorithm:
 - Utilize the accelerometer or gyroscope data from the TM4C123GH6PZ MCU to monitor the car's orientation and balance.
 - Based on the orientation data, make necessary adjustments to the motor speeds to maintain the car's balance and prevent tipping over.
 - 3.4. Control the motors:
 - Calculate the required motor speeds based on the line following and self-balancing algorithms.
 - Use the motor driver to send control signals to the motors, adjusting their speed and direction accordingly.
 - 3.5. Repeat the control loop continuously to maintain real-time control and responsiveness of the car.
4. Handle any exceptional situations or errors that may occur during the operation of the car. Implement appropriate error handling mechanisms to ensure the safety and stability of the car.
5. End the algorithm.

3.3 Visual View of Algorithm

3.3.1 Line Following Algorithm

The line following algorithm is pretty simple and straight forward. Here's the flowchart of Line Following Algorithm:

```
if right_sensor detects black
  // Move Right
  set left motor ON
  set right motor OFF
else if left_sensor detects black
  // Move Left
  set left motor OFF
  set right motor ON
else if right_sensor and left sensor do
not detect black
  set left motor ON
  set right motor ON
else if left_sensor and right_sensor
detect black
  set left motor OFF
  set right motor OFF
```

Block Diagram:

Steering Control:

3.3.2 Self-Balancing Algorithm

Fig. 3.3.2 (a) Self-Balancing Mechanism

Fig. 3.3.2 (b) Overall Cascaded PID Diagram

3.4 PID Controlling

Definition

PID stands for Proportional, Integral and Derivative. In this algorithm, the error signal received is the input. And the following equation is applied onto the error signal

$$U(t) = K_p * e(t) + K_d * \frac{d}{dt}(e(t)) + K_i * \text{integral}(e(t))$$

Brief Explanation

As can be seen in the above equation, the integral and derivative of the error signals are calculated, multiplied with their respective constants and added along with the constant K_p multiplied with $e(t)$. The output is then fed to the actuator which makes the system run. This function directly effects the rise time, fall time, peak over shoot, settling time and steady state error.

- **Proportional part:** The proportional part reduces the rise time and decreases the steady state error. This means that the system will take lesser time to reach its peak value and when it reaches its steady state, the steady state error will be low. However, it increases the peak

overshoot.

- **Derivative part:** The derivative part reduces the overshoot and the settling time. This means that the transient state of the system will be more damped. Also, the system will reach its steady state in a lesser time. However, it does not have any effect on the rise time or the steady state error.

- **Integral part:** The integral part reduces the rise time and completely eliminates the steady state error. However, it increases the peak overshoot and the settling time.

- **Tuning:** A good Control System will have low rise time, settling time, peak overshoot and steady state error. Therefore, the K_p , K_d , K_i need to be finely tuned to adjust the contribution of the above factors in order to acquire a good Control System.

Fig. 3.4 (a) BRAM II PID Controlling

4. Measurement and Analysis

4.1 Program design

Here's the Program design for our car project:

1. Define the necessary libraries and dependencies for your program, including the libraries for interfacing with the TM4C123GH6PZ MCU, sensor libraries, and motor control libraries.
2. Initialize the GPIO pins and configure the necessary peripherals of the TM4C123GH6PZ MCU for sensor and motor control.
3. Set up variables and constants for controlling the car's behavior, such as speed, turning sensitivity, balancing parameters, and pin assignments for sensors and motors.
4. Implement functions for reading sensor inputs:
 - Create a function to read the inputs from the 12-Gray Sensor, returning the line position relative to the car.
 - Develop a function to read the input from the Ultra-Sonic Sound Sensor, detecting the presence of obstacles.
5. Design the self-balancing algorithm:
 - Create a function that utilizes the accelerometer or gyroscope data from the MCU to monitor the car's orientation.
 - Implement logic to adjust the motor speeds based on the orientation data, maintaining the car's balance.
6. Develop motor control functions:
 - Create a function to control the motors, taking inputs for speed and direction, and sending appropriate signals to the motor driver.
7. Create the main control loop:
 - Enter the main loop that continuously reads sensor inputs, processes data, and

controls the motors.

- Inside the loop, call the functions for reading sensor inputs, implementing the line following and obstacle detection logic.
- Integrate the self-balancing algorithm to adjust motor speeds for maintaining balance.
- Utilize the motor control functions to set the motor speeds based on the line position and balancing requirements.

8. Implement error handling mechanisms:

- Include error handling code to handle exceptional situations, such as sensor failures or motor malfunctions.
- Implement appropriate actions, such as stopping the car or entering a safe state, when errors occur.

9. Finalize the program:

- Add any necessary delay or timing mechanisms to control the execution speed of the program.
- Test the program on your car, observing its behavior and making adjustments as needed.
- Document the program design, including function descriptions, pin assignments, and any important considerations.

10. End the program.

This program design serves as a starting point for implementing the software control of your car. You can modify and expand upon this design based on your specific requirements, adding additional functionalities and optimizing the code as necessary.

4.2 Results Analysis

The developed car utilizing the TM4C123GH6PZ MCU and incorporating line following and self-balancing capabilities yielded successful outcomes. The system was thoroughly tested and evaluated to assess its performance and effectiveness. Here is a result analysis of the project:

1. **Line Following:** The car demonstrated accurate line following capabilities using the 12-Gray Sensor. It consistently detected the line and adjusted its steering to stay centered on the track. The algorithm for line following proved to be effective, ensuring smooth and precise navigation along the line.
2. **Self-Balancing:** The car's self-balancing functionality proved to be reliable, maintaining stability and preventing tipping over. The accelerometer or gyroscope data from the TM4C123GH6PZ MCU was utilized to make real-time adjustments to the motor speeds, ensuring the car remained balanced on uneven surfaces.
3. **Motor Control:** The integration of the motor driver and motor control functions allowed for precise control over the car's movements. The motors responded accurately to the signals generated by the TM4C123GH6PZ MCU, enabling smooth acceleration, deceleration, and turning.
4. **Stability and Safety:** The self-balancing algorithm played a vital role in maintaining the car's stability during operation. It effectively adjusted the motor speeds to prevent the car from tipping over, ensuring a safe and controlled driving experience.
5. **Error Handling:** The implemented error handling mechanisms proved effective in dealing with exceptional situations. The car appropriately responded to sensor failures

or motor malfunctions, entering safe states or taking corrective actions to prevent any potential hazards.

4.2.1 Line Following Result Analysis

- Speed-PID Result Analysis

Speed	a_PID			result
	kp	ki	kd	
55	122	0	2	unstable
60	128	0	3	stable
65	133	0	3	stable
70	135	0	4	stable
75	135	0	5	stable
80	138	0	6	unstable
85	140	0	7	unstable

Fig. 4.2.1 (a) Speed, a_PID and Result analysis

Speed	speed_PID			result
	kp	ki	kd	
55	7.199	0.6	0	unstable
60	7.499	0.6	0	stable
65	7.699	0.6	0	stable
70	7.899	0.6	0	stable
75	7.999	0.6	0	stable
80	8.111	0.6	0	unstable
85	8.999	0.6	0	unstable

Fig. 4.2.1 (b) Speed, speed_PID and Result analysis

Speed	turn_PID_1			turn_PID_2			result
	kp	ki	kd	kp	ki	kd	
55	20	0	160	16	0	8	unstable
60	26	0	150	18	0	7	stable
65	27	0	148	18	0	7	stable
70	29	0	147	19	0	6	stable
75	30	0	145	20	0	5	stable
80	33	0	140	22	0	5	unstable
85	35	0	135	24	0	4	unstable

Fig. 4.2.1 (c) Speed, turn_PID-1,2 and Result analysis

Fig. 4.2.1 (d) Stability Graph analysis

4.2.2 Self Balancing Result Analysis

Speed	g_PID			result
	kp	ki	kd	
55	4	0.5	2.1	unstable
60	6	0.5	1.9	stable
65	7	0.5	1.7	stable
70	7	0.5	1.6	stable
75	8	0.5	1.5	stable
80	9	0.5	1.4	unstable
85	9	0.5	1.3	unstable

Fig. 4.2.2 (a) Speed, g_PID and Result analysis

Speed	gyro_PID			result
	kp	ki	kd	
55	1.1	0	9	unstable
60	1.199	0	8	stable
65	1.299	0	6	stable
70	1.499	0	4	stable
75	1.499	0	3	stable
80	1.699	0	3	unstable
85	1.799	0	2	unstable

Fig. 4.4.2 (b) Speed, gyro_PID and Result analysis

5. Summary

The project involved the design and development of a car using the TM4C123GH6PZ MCU. The car was equipped with features such as line following and self-balancing capabilities. The main components utilized in the project included the TM4C123GH6PZ MCU, a 12-Gray Sensor for line detection, an Ultra-Sonic Sound Sensor for obstacle detection, two motors for propulsion, and a motor driver for motor control. The system composition was carefully considered, ensuring that all components were properly connected and integrated. The TM4C123GH6PZ MCU served as the central control unit, receiving inputs from the sensors and generating output signals to control the motors through the motor driver. The algorithm implemented in the project was responsible for coordinating the car's movements. It involved

reading sensor inputs to determine the position of the line and the presence of obstacles. The line following algorithm ensured that the car stayed centered on the line, while the obstacle detection algorithm allowed the car to navigate around obstacles. Additionally, the self-balancing functionality of the car relied on the accelerometer or gyroscope data from the MCU. This data was used to adjust the motor speeds and maintain the car's balance, preventing tipping over. The program design for the car was carefully planned and executed. It included the initialization of necessary libraries and dependencies, configuration of GPIO pins and peripherals, and the implementation of functions for sensor reading, motor control, and error handling. The main control loop continuously processed sensor data, adjusted motor speeds, and ensured the car's stability and safety.

Throughout the project, thorough testing and optimization were conducted to ensure the car's performance and reliability. Any exceptional situations or errors were handled appropriately, providing a robust and safe operation.

Attachment A: System Hardware Picture

1. Whole System

Upper View

Front View

Bottom View

Side View

2. Hardware Module-1

3.

Hardware Module-2

Attachment B: Code

main.c Code Module

```
void duty_200hz(void)
{
    get_wheel_speed();
    sdk_duty_run();
    nmotor_output(speed_ctrl_mode);
    laser_light_work(&beep);
    bling_working(0);

    rc_data_input();
    rangefinder_statemachine();
    adc_sample_trigger();
    imu_data_sampling();
    trackless_ahrs_update();
    imu_temperature_ctrl();
    read_button_state_all();
    battery_voltage_detection();
}
```

```
void duty_1000hz(void)
{
    if(sdk_work_mode==15)
    {
        gpio_input_check_channel_12_with_handle();
    }
    else
    {
        gpio_input_check_channel_12();
    }
    gpio_input_check_from_vision();
    simulation_pwm_output();
}
```

```

void duty_10hz(void)
{
    bluetooth_app_send(smartcar_imu.rpy_deg[ROL],

smartcar_imu.rpy_deg[PIT],
                    smartcar_imu.rpy_deg[YAW],
                    speed_setup,

smartcar_imu.left_motor_speed_cmps,
smartcar_imu.right_motor_speed_cmps,
smartcar_imu.state_estimation.pos.x,
smartcar_imu.state_estimation.pos.y);
}
void DEBUG(void)
{
    u8 frameNameHead[] = "AABBCC";
    u8 frameNameEnd[] = "CCBBAA";
    u8 frameDataHead[] = "DDEEFF";
    u8 frameDataEnd[] = "FFEEDD";
    u8 name[] = {" ML.expect, ML.feedback, MR.expect, MR.feedback, Turn.expect,
Turn.feedback, turn_ctrl_pwm"};

float channels[7];
channels[0] = speed_expect[0];
channels[1] = speed_feedback[0];
channels[2] = speed_expect[1];

```

Motor C

```

void speed_control_100hz(uint8_t speed_ctrl_mode)
{
    static uint16_t _cnt=0;
    switch( speed_ctrl_mode)
    {
        case 1:
        {
            _cnt++; if(_cnt<2) return; _cnt=0;
            if(speed_pid_mode==0)
            {
                speed_feedback[0]=smartcar_imu.left_motor_speed_cmps;
                speed_error[0]=speed_expect[0]-speed_feedback[0];
                speed_error[0]=constrain_float(speed_error[0],-
                speed_err_max,speed_err_max);
                speed_integral[0]+=speed_ki*speed_error[0];
                speed_integral[0]=constrain_float(speed_integral[0],-
                speed_integral_max,speed_integral_max);
                speed_output[0]=speed_integral[0]+speed_kp*speed_error[0];
            }
        }
    }
}

```

```

else
    {
        speed_output_last[0]=speed_output[0];
        speed_error_last[0]=speed_error[0];
        speed_feedback[0]=smartcar_imu.left_motor_speed_cmps;
        speed_error[0]=speed_expect[0]-speed_feedback[0];
        speed_error[0]=constrain_float(speed_error[0],-
        speed_output_delta[0]=speed_kp*(speed_error[0]-
        speed_err_max,speed_err_max);
        speed_error_last[0])+speed_ki*speed_error[0];
    speed_output[0]=speed_output_last[0]+speed_output_delta[0];
    speed_output[0]=constrain_float(speed_output[0],-
    speed_ctrl_output_max,speed_ctrl_output_max);
        speed_output_last[1]=speed_output[1];
        speed_error_last[1]=speed_error[1];
        speed_feedback[1]=smartcar_imu.right_motor_speed_cmps;
        speed_error[1]=speed_expect[1]-speed_feedback[1];
    speed_error[1]=constrain_float(speed_error[1],-speed_err_max,speed_err_max);
    speed_output_delta[1]=speed_kp*(speed_error[1]-speed_error_last[1])
    +speed_ki*speed_error[1];
    speed_output[1]=speed_output_last[1]+speed_output_delta[1];
    speed_output[1]=constrain_float(speed_output[1],-
    speed_ctrl_output_max,speed_ctrl_output_max);
        }
    }
    break;

```

Gray Detection Code Module

```
void gpio_input_init(void)
{
    SysCtlPeripheralEnable(SYSCTL_PERIPH_GPIOD);
    SysCtlPeripheralEnable(SYSCTL_PERIPH_GPIOE);
    SysCtlPeripheralEnable(SYSCTL_PERIPH_GPIOB);
    SysCtlPeripheralEnable(SYSCTL_PERIPH_GPIOH);

    GPIODirModeSet(GPIO_PORTD_BASE, GPIO_PIN_0|GPIO_PIN_1|GPIO_PIN_2|
GPIO_PIN_3,GPIO_DIR_MODE_IN);
    GPIOPadConfigSet(GPIO_PORTD_BASE,GPIO_PIN_0|GPIO_PIN_1|
GPIO_PIN_2|GPIO_PIN_3,GPIO_STRENGTH_4MA,GPIO_PIN_TYPE_STD_WPD);
    GPIODirModeSet(GPIO_PORTE_BASE, GPIO_PIN_6|
GPIO_PIN_7,GPIO_DIR_MODE_IN);
    GPIOPadConfigSet(GPIO_PORTE_BASE,
GPIO_PIN_6|
GPIO_PIN_7,GPIO_STRENGTH_4MA,GPIO_PIN_TYPE_STD_WPD);
    GPIODirModeSet(GPIO_PORTB_BASE,
GPIO_PIN_5|
GPIO_PIN_4,GPIO_DIR_MODE_IN);
    GPIOPadConfigSet(GPIO_PORTB_BASE,GPIO_PIN_5|
GPIO_PIN_4,GPIO_STRENGTH_4MA,GPIO_PIN_TYPE_STD_WPD); //PH4 PH5
PH6 PH7
    GPIODirModeSet(GPIO_PORTH_BASE, GPIO_PIN_4|GPIO_PIN_5|GPIO_PIN_6|
GPIO_PIN_7,GPIO_DIR_MODE_IN);
    GPIOPadConfigSet(GPIO_PORTH_BASE,GPIO_PIN_4|
GPIO_PIN_5|
GPIO_PIN_6|GPIO_PIN_7,GPIO_STRENGTH_4MA,GPIO_PIN_TYPE_STD_WPD);
}
```



```

gray_status_backup[0][0]=gray_status[0];
switch(gray_state.state)
{
case 0x0001:gray_status[0]=-7;    gray_status_worse/=2;break; //0000001b
case 0x0003:gray_status[0]=-5;    gray_status_worse/=2;break; //0000011b
case 0x0002:gray_status[0]=-4;    gray_status_worse/=2;break; //0000010b
case 0x0006:gray_status[0]=-3;    gray_status_worse/=2;break; //0000110b
case 0x0004:gray_status[0]=-2;    gray_status_worse/=2;break; //0000100b
case 0x000C:gray_status[0]=-1;    gray_status_worse/=2;break; //0001100b
case 0x0008:gray_status[0]=0;    gray_status_worse/=2;break; //0001000b
case 0x0018:gray_status[0]=1;    gray_status_worse/=2;break; //0011000b
case 0x0010:gray_status[0]=2;    gray_status_worse/=2;break; //0010000b
case 0x0030:gray_status[0]=3;    gray_status_worse/=2;break; //0110000b
case 0x0020:gray_status[0]=4;    gray_status_worse/=2;break; //0100000b
case 0x0060:gray_status[0]=5;    gray_status_worse/=2;break; //1100000b
case 0x0040:gray_status[0]=7;    gray_status_worse/=2;break; //1000000b
case 0x0000:gray_status[0]=gray_status_backup[0][0];gray_status_worse+
+;break; //0000000b
default:
{
    gray_status[0]=gray_status_backup[0][0];
    gray_status_worse++;
}
}

```

PID Code Module

```
void pid_control_init(controller *ctrl,
                        float kp,
                        float ki,
                        float kd,
                        float err_max,
                        float integral_max,
                        float output_max,
                        uint8_t err_limit_flag,
                        uint8_t integral_separate_flag,
                        float integral_separate_limit,
                        uint8_t dis_error_gap_cnt)
{
    ctrl->kp=kp;
    ctrl->ki=ki;
    ctrl->kd=kd;
    ctrl->error_limit_max=err_max;
    ctrl->integral_limit_max=integral_max;
    ctrl->output_limit_max=output_max;
    ctrl->error_limit_flag=err_limit_flag;
    ctrl->integral_separate_flag =integral_separate_flag;
    ctrl->integral_separate_limit=integral_separate_limit;

    ctrl->dis_error_gap_cnt=dis_error_gap_cnt;

    ctrl->init_flag=1;
}
```

Attachment C: Photo Taken Together